

Determination of Mercaptans and Xanthates with Chloramine-T and Chloramine-B

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An accurate and direct titrimetric procedure has been described for the determination of mercaptans and sodium and potassium salts of alkyl xanthates by oxidation with chloramine-T and Chloramine-B in the presence of potassium iodide. Mercaptans are titrated in dilute acetic acid medium while xanthates in bicarbonate solution. The end point was determined visually using starch as indicator. The procedure is accurate to $\pm 0.4\%$ with a precision of $\pm 0.3\%$

ANALOGOUS compounds of oxygen and sulphur show marked difference in chemical properties.

The hydrogen of the sulphhydryl-SH group displays remarkable reactivity in contrast to its hydroxyl counterpart, undoubtedly because of the larger atomic size of the sulphur atom with consequent longer atomic bond and smaller atomic energy. Mercaptans, being the most tractable of the organic sulphur compounds by virtue of the reactive nature of the sulphhydryl group-SH, have been determined by numerous methods involving a variety of procedures and techniques incorporated with them. Data regarding estimation of mercaptans with chloramine-T are meagre and with Chloramine-B missing. The only attempt made by Mahadevappa³ deals with the estimation of thioglycollic acid with chloramine-T. The present communication embodies the systematic studies to evolve suitable procedures for the quantitative determination of a number of mercaptans. It has been found that in presence of potassium iodide chloramine-T and chloramine-B smoothly, rapidly and quantitatively oxidize mercaptans at room temperature to the corresponding disulphides with a single electron change. The oxidation observes the following course, consuming one mole of chloramine-T and chloramine-B in each case.

The direct method is simple, accurate and instantaneous.

Matuszak³ zetetically discussed the difficulty encountered in the previously reported methods for the analysis of xanthate samples by iodimetry⁴. The basis for the iodimetric method is the quantitative oxidation of the xanthate to the corresponding dixanthogen. The determination of carbon-di-sulphide involves its conversion to and determination as xanthate. Chloramine-T procedure reports higher results than those of the iodimetric determination⁵. In Afanasev's method⁶, titrations with chloramine-T are taken to a bleached indicator end point, methyl red was used for clear solutions and indigo carbmine for coloured solutions. In this oxidation 0.5 mole of the reagent is consumed per mole of xanthate and the accuracy was claimed to

three figures for 0.1-0.2 g. samples. Rao et al.⁷ proposed a back titration method based upon the following equation.

The present communication reports the results of the determination of a variety of sodium and potassium salts of alkyl xanthates based upon their oxidation to their corresponding dixanthogens with the help of chloramine-T and chloramine-B in the presence of potassium iodide and sodium bicarbonate according to the following reaction.

The direct method is simple, accurate and instantaneous.

The procedure for the determination of xanthates has been applied to carbon-di-sulphide, involving conversion to xanthate by potassium ethoxide followed by titration with chloramine-B.

Experimental

Reagent and Samples : 0.01M solutions⁸ of chloramine-T and chloramine-B were prepared⁹ by dissolving an appropriate quantity of the sample in distilled water, standardized by the method of Bishop¹⁰ or by the method of Bottger¹¹, and stored in dark.

Most of the Mercaptan samples were gifts from Evans Chemitics, New York. Some mercaptans and all xanthates were prepared and purified by the authors. All other chemicals were of C. P. grade.

Method for Determining Mercaptans and xanthates : A sample containing 0.1-1.0 m mole of mercaptan or potassium or sodium salt of xanthate was weighed in a 150 ml Erlenmeyer flask and dissolved in 30-50 ml of water. For water insoluble mercaptans 5-10 ml of glacial acetic acid was used to dissolve

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the sample and at the time of titration sufficient amount of water was added to bring acid concentration 30% v/v. About 100 mg of potassium iodide and 1 ml of 1% starch sol. were added about 2 g. of sodium hydrogen carbonate was also added when xanthates were determined. This was titrated with 0.02M chloramine-T and chloramine-B solutions, a blue colour of starch-iodine serves to detect the end point. Neither the end point nor the reaction itself is hampered by the precipitation of some of the disulphides. During the course of titration, reaction mixture should be shaken vigorously.

Method for determining carbon-di-sulphide with chloramine-B.

A sample containing 0.1-1.0 m mole of carbon disulphide was weighed in a small sealed glass bulb and placed in a 150-ml Erlenmeyer flask having 0.5-2.0 ml of 10% potassium ethoxide and 5 ml absolute ethanol. The bulb was broken to release the sample and contents were swirled for 2 min. The flask was cooled in an ice-bath and 30 ml of water and 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator were added, it was titrated with 1M acetic acid solution until the contents were acid to indicator. The potassium ethylxanthate formed was titrated with chloramine-B using the general method described for xanthates.

Results and Discussion

In Table-1, results for the determination of several mercaptans are summarized. Recoveries found by titration with chloramine-T and chloramine-B are compared with those obtained by existing methods. Results for the determination of xanthates and carbon-disulphide are given in Table 2, each of the results is

compared with iodimetric assay^{1,2,13} method. Titration results of mercaptans and xanthates in the presence of various foreign substances are summarized in Table 3. The compounds chosen to study the effect included compounds that interfere in the methods reported in past and compounds that contain other sulphur bearing function. Hydrogen sulphide, thiocarboxyl compounds interfere seriously.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF XANTHATES AND CARBONDISULPHIDE WITH CHLORAMINE-T AND CHLORAMINE-B.

Samples	Purity %		Iodine Titration (12, 13)
	Chloramine-T	Chloramine-B	
K Methyl Xanthate	96.6	96.4	96.8
K ethyl Xanthate	90.7	90.8	90.5
Na ethyl Xanthate	90.3	89.8	90.2
K <i>n</i> -propyl Xanthate	98.8	98.5	98.7
Na <i>n</i> -propyl Xanthate	98.8	98.7	99.1
K iso propyl Xanthate	94.0	94.0	93.8
Na iso-propyl Xanthate	99.7	99.6	99.5
K <i>n</i> -butyl Xanthate	92.6	92.4	92.8
Na Sec. butyl Xanthate	97.6	97.5	97.3
K iso-butyl Xanthate	92.4	92.2	92.0
K amyl Xanthate	96.6	96.2	96.5
K iso-amyl Xanthate	94.5	94.9	94.6
K allyl Xanthate	93.3	93.5	93.2
K cyclohexyl Xanthate	95.5	75.2	75.4
K sec. butyl Xanthate	99.1	98.6	99.0
Carbon disulphide	—	89.8	89.3

Average of 10 determinations, the spread of average deviation is 0.2-0.3%

Mercaptans are titrated without adding acid in the reaction mixture. There should not be any trace of acid while titrating xanthates because they decompose in presence of acid. Under the described conditions of titration, 3-mercaptopropionic, mercaptosuccinic,

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS WITH CHLORAMINE-T AND CHLORAMINE-B.

Mercaptans	Purity %			Ref.
	Chloramine-T*	Chloramine-B*	Comparison Method	
2-Mercaptobenzothiazol	99.0	98.8	99.1 Pb ⁴⁺ Titration	(14)
2-Butane thiol	97.1	97.0	97.3 Iodimetry	(15)
Toluene α -thiol	98.9	98.7	98.8 Acetylation	(16)
Benzene thiol	99.2	99.0	99.4 Pb ⁴⁺ Titration	(14)
Methyl 3-Mercaptopropionate	95.9	95.8	96.1 Iodimetry	(15)
<i>p</i> -chlorotoluene α -thiol	98.9	98.7	99.0 Pb ⁴⁺ Titration	(14)
Thiobenzoic acid	95.1	95.0	94.8 Iodimetry	(15)
2-Mercaptoethanol	99.5	99.6	99.3 Pb ⁴⁺ Titration	(14)
1-Butane thiol	99.3	99.0	99.2 Acetylation	(16)
1-Pentane thiol	88.4	88.0	88.2 Iodimetry	(15)
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	97.0	97.1	96.8 Iodimetry	(15)
Toluene thiol (mixed isomers)	93.0	93.2	92.8 Acetylation	(16)
Allyl thiol	92.8	92.9	93.1 Pb ⁴⁺ Titration	(14)
Mercaptoacetic acid	80.2	80.3	80.0 Iodimetry	(15)
1-Propane thiol	95.3	95.4	95.0 Pb ⁴⁺ Titration	(14)
<i>m</i> -Mercaptobenzoic acid	99.5	99.6	99.3 Iodimetry	(15)
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzene thiol	99.4	99.6	99.5 Nitrite titration	(17)
2-Naphthalene thiol	99.2	99.1	99.5 Pb ⁴⁺ Titration	(14)
Glutathione	97.8	97.7	98.1 Iodimetry	(18)
<i>p</i> -Toluene thiol	98.5	98.7	98.3 Iodimetry	(15)
2-Diethylaminoethane thiol hydrochloride	99.5	99.4	99.7 Iodimetry	(15)
2-Mercaptoethyl ammonium chloride	99.3	99.2	99.5 Iodimetry	(15)

*Average of 10 determinations, the spread of average deviation is 0.2-0.3%

TABLE 3—INTERFERENCES IN TITRATION OF MERCAPTANS AND XANTHATES WITH CHLORAMINE-T AND CHLORAMINE-B.

Sample	Titratant	Compound Added	Molar ratio added compd./sample	Sample Recovery (%) [*]
Thiobenzoic acid	Chloramine-T	Carbon-di-sulphide	56 : 1	100.6
		Allyl alcohol	49 : 1	100.6
		Diphenyldisulphide	16 : 1	100.0
		Alanine	43 : 1	100.8
K. cyclóhexyl Xanthate	Chloramine-T	Glycine	39 : 1	100.1
		Acetone	52 : 1	98.6
		Acrylonitrile	40 : 1	99.4
		Urea	41 : 1	100.2
		Thiophene	19 : 1	102.0
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	Chloramine-B	Dextrose	95 : 1	100.0
		Methyl acrylate	27 : 1	99.6
		Dibenzyl sulphide	10 : 1	100.0
		Sodium chloride	107 : 1	99.9
		Potassium bromide	5 : 1	100.0
Na-sec. butyl Xanthate	Chloramine-B	Dimethyl sulfoxide	40 : 1	99.8
		Dodecyl sulphate	34 : 1	100.4
		Cinnamic acid	40 : 1	100.0
Toluene α -thiol	Chloramine-T	Diphenyl sulphide	12 : 1	100.0
		Sulphosalicylic acid	8 : 1	100.0
		Diphenyl disulphide	18 : 1	100.0
		Carbon-di-sulphide	50 : 1	100.2

^{*}Average of 4 determinations, % recovery takes into account the previously determined purity of the samples.

o-mercaptobenzoic acid having a carboxyl group on a carbon atom β to the mercapto group and cysteine could not be determined. In each case there is an excessive consumption of the oxidant which varied from one titration to another in an unaccountable fashion.

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